

APPLICATION OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK.

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Abstract: *In this article, we will study the Karakalpak and English versions of proverbs from the history of the people and their methods and meanings. The proverb was considered to be a wise saying that lived with this people and passed down from generation to generation. Proverbs are based on the way of life and history of a nation and have been passed down from father to son over the years. Such wise sayings are also uttered in English and Karakalpak. Although they do not have literal equivalents, it is possible that they are similar in meaning. Each proverb has a deep meaning and encourages people to be united and live on the basis of proverbs.*

Key Words: *proverb, paremiology, paroemia, Miguel de Cervantes, folklore, a folk proverb.*

INTRODUCTION: Proverbs are a very concise, yet meaningful, form of folklore. The proverb is the culmination of the mind and experience of the people, the product of the wisdom of the people.

"Proverbs are the beauty of words," our people say. Look, the people also used proverbs to describe the importance of proverbs.

Proverbs are the cream of speech, the essence of conversation, the essence of what is said in large and small circles, in meetings.

Ideologically, proverbs are very diverse and colorful. Folk proverbs cover all aspects of life in many ways. In folk proverbs about the Motherland, the ideas of devotion to the Motherland are embodied in a very concise, rich and melodic form.

In folk proverbs, labor is described as the basis of material and spiritual wealth, the beauty of man.

In Spanish literature, Miguel de Cervantes said "Proverbs are short sentences drawn from long experience". The same is said of the place of proverbs for Romano-Germanic literature and its people, and that a great deal of time is spent on their formation.

In proverbs, the value of words is especially vivid. Because you can't replace words in proverbs with words. They appear in the structure of the national language. This genre is present in the oral art of all peoples of the world and is considered to be common in terms of size, shape and purpose of creation. Even in the naming, the closeness is clearly felt. For example, in Arabic, "qawlun" means a word, in the Tajik term "zarbulmasal", in the Russian "proverb" it is expressed in words, and in the Turks "ota sozi" it means to remember the opinion of ancestors. In Mahmud Kashgari's *Devonu lug'otit turk*, the term "sav" is also used to remember the word father.

So, the term proverb is related to the concept of "word" in general.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION:

Folklore scholars call the field of study of proverbs and parables paremiology. Paroemia (proverbs) is a Greek word meaning a profound word, a word of wisdom, a phrase, a proverb, a proverb.

The genre features of your article are:

1. The size of your proverb is short and limited.
2. Proverbs have a rich and profound meaning.
3. Folk proverbs take the form of poetry and prose. But prose is also reminiscent of poetry.
4. Proverbs express a firm judgment about a life event. This judgment is reflected in a positive or negative context.
5. The proverb summarizes the special situation in the life of a person in terms of people, community, life.
6. The text of a proverb is generalized sentence in linguistics.

So, we have a general idea about the proverbs and now we can compare the proverbs in Karakalpak and English and see their similarities and differences. Articles in English cannot be literally translated into Karakalpak, but articles with the same content can also be translated into Karakalpak.

Let us consider our point in the example of some proverbs.

- 1) A fool at forty is a fool forever

Meaning: If a person hasn't matured by the age of 40, they never will. In other words, it is said that a person's mind must grow together as he grows older, and that every step he takes must be passed on to the next generation, especially his own children. Otherwise, his life as a human being is meaningless. Explains that in order to live happily, one must not only live but also live wisely.

- 2) The apple never falls far from the tree

Meaning: Children are in many regards like their parents. Man must live in this life not only for himself but also for his children. He has to teach them what he knows, how to live life. Children do not do what their parents tell them to do, they do what they do. This article also says that a person should be an example to his child through his actions.

- 3) All things come to those who wait

Meaning: A patient seeker will be satisfied in due time Man will surely achieve what he wants, and for this he will only need to be patient. A person may face many problems in his life, but he must still be patient and strong-willed and continue to live and move. The reward of patience will be great. As the saying goes, beautiful things come with patience and time.

- 4) A friend in need is a friend indeed

Meaning: A friend is never known till a man has need. A friend should act as a mirror to the person. Man becomes like his friend. Because if you spend a lot of time

with someone, then his habits will become a habit for you too, and this will lead to the emergence of similarities between the two people. But one should never look for a flawless friend because everyone has flaws and one should accept them with flaws and help them get rid of them.

5) Bad news travels fast

Meaning: Information about trouble or misfortune disseminates quickly. There is not always good news in a person's life, but there can also be bad news in a person's life. And the most interesting aspect is that people tend to convey bad news to each other and therefore bad news starts to spread very quickly.

6) Beauty is in the eyes of the beholder

Meaning: Different people have different ideas about what is beautiful. Everyone has a different answer to the question about beauty because everyone has less worldview and taste. Therefore, it would not be a mistake to consider beauty as a relative concept. But if a person likes someone, then the flaw in that person in his eyes also looks beautiful and he does not notice the mistakes in them.

7) A burnt child dreads the fire

Meaning: You will avoid an activity which has given you a bad experience for the rest of your life. If a person makes a mistake in his life, then he will do his best not to make that mistake again. But just as a horse clicks seven times one place that it does not want to click it again, it makes the same mistake several times and makes an experiment. In fact, it is necessary to draw conclusions from these mistakes without fear of making a mistake, so that the mistake can not be repeated.

8) Don't count your chickens before they're hatched

Meaning: You should not count on something before it happens. It is not possible to comment or make a decision about something before it happens. This can lead to many losses and a large error can occur. The best way is to observe and be patient until the end.

CONCLUSION: So, no matter what topic, no matter what area of life is considered in folk proverbs, the chosen problem is covered in detail. All this proves how wise and intelligent creative children the people have for centuries.

Learning proverbs based on two languages and comparing languages can be of great help. Their lives will be much easier if they follow the rules of ethics and take the necessary content from proverbs. The proverb always lives among people and mobilizes them to enhance their spiritual world. This means that by organizing, memorizing, and using proverbs in daily life, they can live on words that come from history and have been tested.

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